

Some Observations on the Kinetics and Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions in Solution

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Investigations have been carried out on the kinetics of dissociation in acid (HClO_4) medium of the chelate complexes formed by chromium (III) and cobalt (III) with biguanide, hexylⁿ biguanide, and phenylbiguanide. In acid medium the dissociation reaction can be represented as:

where M stands for Cr (III) or Co (III) and BH for a molecule of any biguanide. It is probably needless to point out that the species (ii) will also have two molecules of water (not shown) in order to satisfy the co-ordination number six of the metal. The species (ii) will further dissociate in a similar manner affording the mono-(biguanide) complex, which in turn will dissociate to the metal ion (aquated). It has been observed, however, that the different steps occur in different acid concentrations, a fact to be expected from the large differences in the formation constants of the mono, bis, and tris complexes in general^{1,2}. Even in the acidity regions, where the consecutive steps occur, the second step is, however, generally very much slow so that the kinetics of the first step can be easily followed, at least in the initial stages of the reaction. The spectrophotometric method, which has been used for following the rates of these reactions, makes use of the sufficiently large differences in the molar absorbance indices of the tris, bis and mono complexes at the λ_{max} which is almost the same (within about 10-20 m μ) for all the species. Measurements of the rate at different acid concentrations indicate that in all the cases, where the reaction could be conveniently followed (Table I), the following rate expression holds good:

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Complex}] [\text{H}^+] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \text{(I)}$$

temperature and ionic strength being maintained constant, the latter with sodium perchlorate. It has been further observed that for both the chromium (III) and cobalt (III) tris complexes, at any particular acid concentration, ionic strength, and temperature, the rate decreases in the following sequence of the ligands:

Biguanide > Hexylⁿ biguanide > Phenylbiguanide.

This is exactly the order of decreasing base strength of the ligands and also of the decreasing stability of the corresponding complexes¹⁻². (Quantitative data for the hexyl¹⁸biguanide complexes are not available in the literature, but these are expected to be intermediate between biguanide and phenylbiguanide complexes). This apparently paradoxical result, as reported above, namely, the greater liability of the more stable species, can be accounted for by a mechanism involving protonation of the complex-bound ligand prior to bond rupture, e.g.:

The structural formula (iii) for the metal-biguanides has been well established by Rây *et al.*^{3,4}. It is clear that the species (iv) will have a greater tendency for bond rupture with the simultaneous entry of two water molecules, possibly in stages:

If k be the rate constant for the dissociation of the species (iv), it can easily be shown that

$$\text{Rate} = k.K [\text{Complex}] [\text{H}^+] = k_{\text{obs}} [\text{Complex}] [\text{H}^+] \quad \dots \quad \text{(II)}$$

where K is the equilibrium constant for the formation of species (iv) from (iii) and H^+ ion. Since the value of K will depend on the base strength of the co-ordinated ligand (which will naturally be related to the base strength of the free ligand) the cause of greater liability of the more stable species is easily understood. It is further interesting to point out in this connection that tris-ethylenediamine-chromium (III) ion, $\text{Cr}(\text{en})_3^{3+}$, dissociates over

On the basis of the above mechanism the complete rate expression will be:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k' \cdot K' \cdot K_w [\text{Complex}] [\text{OH}^-]^{-1} \quad \dots \\ &= k'_{\text{obs}} [\text{Complex}] [\text{OH}^-]^{-1} \quad \dots \quad \text{(IV)} \end{aligned}$$

where k' is the rate constant for the change of species (ix) to (x), K' is the equilibrium constant for the formation of species (ix) from (viii) and H^+ ion, and K_w is the ionic product of water. It may be pointed out that the anhydro-base is known and its formation in alkaline solution has also been indicated during the present investigations by an increase in the molar absorbance index of the complex. These results therefore indicate the kinetic stabilization of chromium(III)-tris-biguanide in alkaline media, an observation of great significance as this explains nicely the fact that this species is formed from freshly precipitated chromium (III) hydroxide and biguanide in strongly alkaline media and is hydrolysed to the bis-complex only in an alkaline medium buffered with excess of ammonium salt⁸. As the phenylbiguanide complex (0.001 M) is precipitated even in dilute alkali medium (0.01 M NaOH), measurements of the rate could not be made in this case. The behaviour of the phenylbiguanide complex is, however, expected to be very similar and it is known that chromium(III)-tris-phenylbiguanide complex is also prepared in hot strongly alkaline medium⁹. It has further been observed that cobalt(III)-tris-biguanide is exceedingly inert in alkaline media to resist any change over a period of one week at 32° in 0.01 to 2.0 M sodium hydroxide solutions; cobalt (III)-tris-ethylenediamine complex is also known¹⁰ to dissociate immeasurably slowly under similar conditions and measurable rate is observed only from 70° onwards.

The activation energies of the various reactions studied have also been determined graphically as usual by making use of the Arrhenius equation. These values are recorded in Table I along with a few typical rate constants.

TABLE I

Kinetics of dissociation of Cr (III) and Co (III) complexes.

Complex: 0.001 M . Ionic strength = 1 M (NaClO_4). Temp. = 35.5°.

[BigH = Biguanide. PhbigH = Phenylbiguanide. HxbigH = Hexyl^a biguanide].

Complex.	HClO_4 .	Observed rate constant $\times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	Activation energy, (k. cal).
	Dissociation in acid.		
$\text{Cr}(\text{BigH})_3^{3+}$	0.01 M	73	12.3
$\text{Cr}(\text{BigH})_2^{3+}$	1.00	4	19.9
$\text{Cr}(\text{PhbigH})_3^{3+}$	0.01	20	17.0
$\text{Cr}(\text{PhbigH})_2^{3+}$	1.00	3	24.0
$\text{Cr}(\text{HxbigH})_3^{3+}$	0.01	24*	16.6
$\text{Co}(\text{BigH})_3^{3+}$	0.10	90	13.6
$\text{Co}(\text{PhbigH})_3^{3+}$	0.10	9	13.5
$\text{Co}(\text{HxbigH})_3^{3+}$	0.05	17*	11.6
	Dissociation in alkali.		
	NaOH.		
$\text{Cr}(\text{Big})_3$	0.2 M	33	24.8

* These runs were carried out in solutions which did not contain any indifferent electrolyte (NaClO_4) for ionic strength adjustment as these complexes were found to be salted out by NaClO_4 .

In this connection it may be interesting to discuss the observations reported by Rây and Dutt¹¹ much earlier on the kinetics of racemization of the cobalt (III) complex (tris) of biguanide. A critical examination of their data indicates that the rate is either independent of H^+ ion or else retarded or accelerated by it, depending on the range of acidity. These results seem to suggest that the complex can racemize by three distinct paths as shown below:

where k 's stand for the reaction rate constants and K 's for respective equilibrium constants. On the basis of the above mechanism it can be shown that

$$\text{Rate} = \{k_1 K_1 / [\text{H}^+] + k_2 + k_3 k_2 [\text{H}^+]\} [\text{Complex}] \quad \dots \quad (\text{V})$$

From equation (V) it follows that, for proper values of the constants, the rate will be either independent of H^+ ion or else there will be retardation or acceleration of the reaction by H^+ ion depending on the acidity range. Although the intramolecular mechanism involving distortion of the molecule without any bond rupture, suggested by Rây and Dutt¹¹, is likely to operate for the species $\text{Co}(\text{BH})_3^{3+}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{BH})_2(\text{B})^{2+}$, the protonated species, $\text{Co}(\text{B}_2\text{H}_2)(\text{BH}_2)^{4+}$, is not unlikely to racemize by bond rupture, at least passing through a five-co-ordinated intermediate due to fission of the chelate ring of the protonated ligand.

A discussion of some of our recent observations, still in progress, on the mechanism of reduction of rhenium (V) to rhenium (IV) by Sn (II) in hydrochloric acid medium seems pertinent. On treating a solution of potassium perrhenate in hydrochloric acid medium with excess of Sn (II) chloride, a green color is formed instantaneously due to reduction of rhenium (VII) to rhenium (V), which is further reduced rather slowly to rhenium (IV)¹². In solutions containing over 3M hydrochloric acid, the rhenium (IV) remains in true solution exhibiting a brownish green colour. We have now made a series of observations on the kinetics of this step to find out the effects of the different species involved in this system on the rate of this reduction process. Our results are in agreement with the following rate expression:

$$\text{Rate} = k''_{\text{obs}} [\text{Re(V)}] [\text{Sn(II)}]^{0.5} [\text{HCl}] \quad \dots \quad (\text{VI})$$

These results can be interpreted on the basis of an atom-transfer mechanism as outlined below:

Making use of the steady state assumption, it can be shown that

$$\text{Rate} = 2k_1[(\text{Re(V)})] [\text{H}_2\text{SnCl}_4] \quad \dots \quad (\text{VII})$$

If we now assume that Sn (II) is present in the experimental medium (3 to 6M-HCl) chiefly in a binuclear form, $\text{H}_2\text{Sn}_2\text{Cl}_6$, which is involved in equilibria of the following types:

$$K' = [\text{HSnCl}_3]^2 / [\text{H}_2\text{Sn}_2\text{Cl}_6]$$

and
$$K'' = [\text{H}_2\text{SnCl}_4] / [\text{HSnCl}_3] / [\text{HCl}]$$

Then since,

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{H}_2\text{SnCl}_4] &= K'^{0.5} \cdot K'' [\text{H}_2\text{Sn}_2\text{Cl}_6]^{0.5} [\text{HCl}] \\ &= 2^{-0.5} \cdot K'^{0.5} K'' [\text{Sn(II)}]^{0.5} [\text{HCl}] \quad \dots \quad (\text{VIII}) \end{aligned}$$

we get from equations ((VII) and (VIII):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= 2^{0.5} \cdot K'^{0.5} \cdot K'' k_1 [\text{Re(V)}] [\text{Sn(II)}]^{0.5} [\text{HCl}] \\ &= k''_{\text{obs}} [(\text{Re(V)})] [\text{Sn(II)}]^{0.5} [\text{HCl}] \quad \dots \quad (\text{IX}) \end{aligned}$$

where [Sn (II)] represents its total concentration in the system.

The mechanism, just outlined above, is in agreement with the well-established formulas of rhenium (V) and rhenium (IV) species likely to be involved under the experimental conditions^{1,2}. Although we have so far no direct experimental evidence as to the binuclear nature of Sn (II) species in hydrochloric acid medium (3 to 6M), this is, however, the only simple way we can account for the 0.5 order dependence of the rate on Sn(II) concentration. It may be pointed out in this connection that although the reaction rate is hardly affected by the presence of potassium chloride (1M) in the solution, it is somewhat retarded by lanthanum chloride and accelerated by potassium bisulphate. Further details of such effects are under investigation. The activation energy of the reaction has also been evaluated in the usual way and it comes out to be about 10kcal. At 35.5° the observed rate constant for 0.003M rhenium (V), 0.06M Sn(II), and 4M-HCl is 0.089 min⁻¹.

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